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A GEO-SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE ROLE OF GOVERNMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CARBON STORAGE SYSTEMS IN NIGERIA: THE JOURNEY TO CLEANER ENERGY.

By

Awujo Emmanuel D.¹ Kehinde O. Alamu², Olabisi. A. Adekeye Ph.D.³

¹Department of Geology and Mineral Sciences University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria

²Department of Geology and Mineral Science, Kwara State University, Malete

³Department of Geology and Mineral Sciences University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria³

Contact

Email: emmanueldaberechukwu@gmail.com, Phone: +2348152184599¹

koluakemi616@gmail.com, Phone: +2348145035625²

ABSTRACT

Over the years, the exploration of oil and gas has been a source of income for some countries around the world, including Nigeria. The above human activity gave birth to many combustible engines, ranging from airplanes to automobiles to cooking stoves, to name a few. Despite this, it has been the most significant contributor to global warming over the past decades, as it is the major source of greenhouse gas released into the atmosphere as a result of human activities, reducing atmospheric carbon dioxide is critical for slowing climate change. Carbon sequestration is a method of mitigating the effects of carbon dioxide by capturing and storing the emitted CO₂. After being moved to a potential storage location, the acquired CO₂ must be stored. This paper, which focuses on carbon storage systems, investigates the role of government in the development of carbon storage systems in Nigeria, ranging from storage locations to the conditions under which carbon can be stored in Nigeria, up to the duration of storage of these carbon and possible re-usability potentials and patterns where necessary. We adopted various analytical methods such as pore spaces analysis, paper review approach, permeability studies, and government policy analysis, all with the goal of bringing to light models that Nigeria could use to advance the development of carbon storage for a more sustainable energy exploration, facilitating its journey to a cleaner energy, for an effective and functional carbon storage facilities will speed up Nigeria's desirability.

Keywords: *Carbon Sequestration, Nigeria, government, oil and gas, storage, development.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most prevalent environmental and energy challenge of our time has been global warming (climate change). This is the release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere as a result of the burning of fossil fuel, specific industrial processes, and other factors which has significantly increased heat retention and reduced outward radiation. Carbon dioxide is currently the most common of these gases, making it the most emitted of them all. Nonetheless, there seems to be a way to circumnavigate the issues of carbon emission, this pathway is what is known as carbon sequestration (Carbon Capture and Storage). CCS which is considered by many scholars as the separation of CO₂ and its capture from mixture of emitted combustion gases, followed by its transportation and appropriate storage under the ground, thereby preventing it from the atmospheric contact (Herzog 1997; Ha-Doung & Keith 2003; Anderson & Newell).

As fossil fuel burns, there is a spontaneous release of larger carbon dioxide, a greenhouse gas into the air. The greenhouse gases trap heat in atmosphere, causing global warming. The emission from fossil fuel is the dominant cause of global warming. Besides carbon dioxide, these fuels are also known to release additional gases, such as methane, Sulphur oxides, and many others. These gases are referred to as greenhouse gases because they permit the incoming solar radiation to pass through them but prevent the trapped heat from escaping.

Fig. 1 Carbon capture and storage schematic.

Source: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:carbon_sequestration_-2009-10-07.svg

The oil and gas industry were one of the pioneers in adopting carbon sequestration. Since then, business owners have become aware of the advantages of utilizing carbon capture and storage technology in their operations. Several oil and gas processes produce streams of CO₂ that are highly concentrated and can be employed in low cost.

Other than releasing carbon containing gases into the environment, oil and gas operators can channel them into natural gas formations to improve dwindling pressure and sustain productivity. Several points in the oil refining process generate large volumes of carbon dioxide gas. For example, CO₂ produced from steam methane reformers can be captured safely for re-use and storage in several oil and gas applications. The deployment of carbon sequestration methods significantly improves the environment, society and governance for oil and gas industry operators. Apart from targeting maximum output from their processes, they also preserve the natural environment, more countries are signing up to reduce their carbon emissions and improve the global climate condition. Consequently, various local and national regulatory bodies have tightened emissions regulations for industrial operators within their jurisdictions.

CCS is a cornerstone for industrial de-carbonization with the potential to create economic growth and jobs, and it is the primary method for the decarbonizing industrial sectors such as cement, steel and fertilizers. Once carbon is captured, it is compressed into liquid state and transported by pipelines, ships, rail, or road tanker, its can then be injected and permanently stored into suitable geological formations, underground, or into the seabed with a depth of 1km or more such as depleted oil and gas reservoir, coal beds or deep saline aquifers where the geology is suitable.

There are numerous ways that CCS can contribute strategically to global de-carbonization initiatives. Among these are: lowering emissions in hard-to-abate business (those that are difficult to decarbonize), producing low-carbon energy and hydrogen, which can be utilized in decarbonization, and the removal of existing CO₂ from the atmosphere. Due to the divisibility of CCS, it can also aid in increasing the variety and adaptability of the energy supply, thereby promoting energy security, which has become an apprehension for government at all levels globally.

In Nigeria, increasing urban and rural population, income levels changes, and energy use are leading to a steady increase in greenhouse gases emissions, Nigeria boasts of a proven reserve of 36.22 billion barrels of oil and 209 trillion cubic feet of gas, and an increasing primary energy consumption of 0.9 to 1.2 quadrillion Btu between 2003 and 2007 (EIA 2006). CCS will require future attention in Nigeria, however, the potential implementation should be identified and addressed ahead of time. In order to bridge this gap, decarbonization across all sectors and industries through the use of practical and economic viable solutions will play a critical role in the actualization of the net-zero greenhouse emissions (GHG) in the country, while the gap between the actualization of net-zero and the cumulative carbon emission grows, all fingers are pointing towards carbon capture, its utilization and sequestration (CCUS) as the bridge in-between the gap. Fig.2 below shows that about 40 million metric tons of carbon is being stored annually by industries, with an increasing storage capability if fifteen (15) to twenty (20) percent yearly, fig.2 also shows the desired global target of 7,600 million metric tons of carbon storage by 2050, as this will make the global quest for a more cleaner and sustainable energy achievable and sustainable.

Fig. 2 Global Carbon Capture Demographics

Source: Slb Carbon Capture and Sequestration.

In line with the above, CCUS plays a vital role in the global decarbonization initiative as one of the few viable mechanisms, nonetheless, it does not come easy but comes with its own challenges, one of which is the establishment of a new market ecosystem which will help put to an end the challenges the world is faced today. Presently, industries are capturing and storing over 40 million metric tons of carbon annually, however, carbon capture, utilization and sequestration are needed at a gigaton scale in order to make the net-zero vision of 2050 a reality.

With the right policies and functional regulatory framework which will in turn bring about the development of cost-effective CCUS projects in Nigeria, for example in the United States of America where policies like the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), this provides small-scale to medium scale CCUS projects with tax incentives for a better chance of becoming more economically viable. In Europe, there has been a revision of the Emission Trade System (ETS), this covers a broader range of sectors and greenhouse gas emissions. In Canada also, the Emission Reduction Alberta (ERA) which is a multimillion dollar allocation for the development of carbon capture projects, likewise in Australia where CCUS has been included in the government policies and budgetary, this paper understudies these policies and its contributions to the actualization of the net-zero initiative, and areas where Nigeria can adopt the functional framework for the actualization of cleaner energy in the country and ultimately key into the global reality of net-zero by 2050.

THE NEED TO DECARBONIZE

Fig 3. Flowchart showing the need for de-carbonization and its benefits

At the end of November 2021, the Global Carbon Project made Public its Global Carbon Budget of 2021, which was a comparative study of the global performance when it comes to carbon emission and this was as follows:

- i.** The average concentration of carbon (CO₂) increased globally from about 277 part per million (ppm) in 1750 to 414ppm in 2020 indicating a 49% increment in CO₂ emission globally.
- ii.** The global CO₂ emission from fossil fuels were 34.8GtCO₂ a 5.4% decrease from the previously known figure of 36.7GtCO₂ in 2019.
- iii.** For 2021, global CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels are projected to grow 4.9% to 36.4 GtCO₂, a level which is about 0.8% below the 2019 level. (The 2021 growth of 1.6 GtCO₂ is similar to the growth observed in 2010 following the global financial crisis of 2008-2009: 1.7 GtCO₂ or 5.5% above 2009 levels.)

However, it is important to know that the Global fossil CO₂ emissions in 2021 are set to rebound close to their pre-COVID levels after an unprecedented drop in 2020. Emissions from coal and gas use are on the other hand were set to grow more in 2021 than they fell in 2020, but emissions from oil use remain below 2019 levels.

The record decrease in 2020 emissions was 1.9 billion tonnes of CO₂ (GtCO₂) [-5.4%], from 36.7 GtCO₂ in 2019 to 34.8 GtCO₂ in 2020. Emissions are projected to grow 4.9% (4.1% to 5.7%) in 2021, to 36.4 GtCO₂. Global emissions in 2021 remain about 0.8% below their level in 2019. The 2021 growth of 1.6 GtCO₂ is similar to the growth observed in 2010 following the global financial crisis of 2008-2009 (1.7 GtCO₂; 5.5% above 2009 levels).

The table in fig. 4 below shows the 2021 global carbon budget, which is calculated breakdown of the amount of CO₂ produced by the living things on the earth, it encompasses all the greenhouse carbon emitted from fossil fuel and other drivers of human civilization.

2021 Global Carbon Budget (November 2021)

1 Gigaton (Gt) = 1 billion tons

YEAR	FOSSIL FUEL (Gt)	LAND USE CHANGE (Gt)	TOTAL Gt
<i>2021</i>	36.4	-	-
<i>2020</i>	34.8	3.2	38.0
<i>2019</i>	36.7	3.8	40.5
<i>2018</i>	36.6	3.9	40.5
<i>2017</i>	35.9	3.7	39.6
<i>2016</i>	35.5	3.7	39.2
<i>2015</i>	35.5	4.8	40.3
<i>2014</i>	35.5	4.6	40.1
<i>2013</i>	35.3	4.3	39.6
<i>2012</i>	35.0	4.7	39.7
<i>2011</i>	34.5	4.8	39.3

**Source data: Global Carbon Project 2021 (via ICOS),
data supplement + global data + national emissions**

It is also imperative to know that during this calculations and plotting which was earlier done CO₂.earth, was done by multiplying carbon emissions in the linked excel data by 3.664 to get 1 value of GtCO₂ also emissions from fossil fuels and land use were also added to get the total emissions. Here, fossil fuels excludes sinks from cement carbonization, finally, global CO₂ emissions for 2021 is a projected data.

The plot contained in fig. 5 below is a graphical representation of the data as interpreted by CO₂.earth, it shows the drastic drop in the amount of CO₂ emissions in the year 2020, this could be said to be as a result of the global lockdown in response to the ravaging caused by Covid-19 which limited human interaction, movement and industrial activities. These curves and results definitely sends one question to our mind, where do these CO₂ go?

Fig. 5 graph showing the global CO₂ emission.

The graph above summarizes all human-caused sources of CO₂ emissions and global sinks (where the CO₂ goes). The numbers present the yearly average for one decade (2011 to 2020). Data were published November 5, 2021, in Global Carbon Budget 2021 by the Global Carbon Project.

Fossil fuel takes the center stage as the leading source of most human-caused CO₂ emission into the atmosphere, these fossil fuels are the product of the transformation of various organic matter that has long been stored in geological formations deep under the earth's subsurface for millions of years, and a very small portion of these fossil fuels is from cement usage. Of all CO₂ emissions, those of the fossil fuels accounts for 89% translating to 34.8GtCO₂ annually, while that of the land use especially from deforestation accounts for 11% that is 4.1GtCO₂ per year

Fig. 6: A fossil fuel burning, B: Land use.

Having examined the causes and CO₂ emission amount globally, it is now time for us to answer that all important question of where do all these carbon go?

Here is your answer, between 2011 and 2020, about 55% of global emissions were absorbed by the terrestrial biosphere and oceans. The remainder were added to the CO₂ which is accumulating in the atmosphere. This accumulation has been observed as continued increases in CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere. About 48% (18.8GtCO₂) were absorbed by the atmosphere yearly, while C on the other hand, about 26% (10.2GtCO₂) were taken in by the oceans.

Fig. 7 showing the location of the carbon absorption

The global carbon budget numbers above are the best available scientific determinations at the time they were reported. Scientists also report an imbalance of 3% (-1.0 GtCO₂/year) between the estimates for global sources, sinks and uncertainties (Friedlingstein et al 2021).

Decarbonization is therefore defined as the process by which the human-caused carbon dioxide (CO₂) reduced to the lowest minimum, a point at which is poses no threat to life, and the ecological balance at large, this include the temperature balance of the planet as well. To effectively decarbonize, there is a need for a well-coordinated global shift to alternative energy sources other than the fossil fuels (coal, oil and gas). Fortunately, decarbonization brings so many benefits beyond environmental protection associated with risk management, health, and value creation and innovation opportunities. These innovation opportunities encompasses those of the carbon capture utilization and storage (CCUS), which will not only decarbonize and accelerate the global quest to an emission free society by 2050, but will enhance the present day economy through the creation jobs and poverty alleviation.

Furthermore, energy usage is remains the leading source of CO₂ emissions and has contributed more than 83% of all emissions globally (Mckinsey, 2021) opined that over 34 billion metric

tons of CO₂ is emitted yearly into the earth's atmosphere. Subsequently, limiting the temperature rise to 1.5°C globally will require a reduction of the global CO₂ emissions by 45% by 2030 and a further reduction by 100% by 2050. In order to achieve the, the world is therefore required to cut down it emissions by 7.6% annually.

Nigerian Carbon Emission Index:

The Nigerian carbon emission index is a representation of the amount of carbon emitted in Nigeria per capita and its global share, as at 2016, Nigeria has a fossil CO₂ emission of 82,634,214 tons with a yearly change of 0.70% which represent a global share of 0.23% and an emission per capita of 0.44. The pie chart in figure 8 below showcases the percentage distribution of carbon emissions in Nigeria, emitted by various sectors of the country as at the year 2016

Fig. 8 fossil fuel emission by sectors in Nigeria in 2016

Consequently, a study of the Nigerian carbon emissions from 2010 to 2022 showed the an exponential growth in the amount of CO₂ emissions in the country, however, it is also an eye opener as to the urgency in the reduction of carbon emission thus placing a huge significance on the carbon storage systems, CCUS which has been adopted in some countries like South Africa, has since seen an increase its usage as the above is linked with its importance to both the storage facility and the storing society like in the case of rejuvenation of depilated well pressure with time.

Between 1990 and 2020, Nigeria experienced a 271% increase in greenhouse gas emissions (Peter Hansen, 2020), the recently reported greenhouse gas emission level of 104.27MtCO₂^e in 2018, indicated an increase of 271.60% from 1990 (source: IEA). Over time, Nigeria's greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) have been increasing steadily, however, between 1996 and 2001 Nigeria witnessed a remarkable drop in its GHG emissions, nonetheless, a dip in Nigeria's GHG emissions as witnessed in 2009 could be attributed to the global financial crisis following 9/11, which resulted in the decrease in the economic production of the country. As seen in

figure 9 below, the Nigerian greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) have tremendously increased, and is still rising spontaneously as years goes by, this is no doubt a worrying trend for future emission projections.

Source: Own manipulation of Climate Watch Data

Fig. 9 Nigeria’s GHG emission curve between 1990 and 2016

According to the international Energy Association, they opined that in 2018 alone Nigeria emitted ±104.27 of MtCO₂e, the figure indicates a 271.6% increase from the 1990 levels of total greenhouse emission in Nigeria. In 2016, the total greenhouse emissions in Nigeria stood at 481.02 MtCO₂e, these emissions comprises of the following: carbon dioxide 61.74%, methane 27.82%, nitrous oxide, 7.7%, and fluorinated gases 2.66%. Figure 10 blow shows a pie chart of the percentage distribution of these G HG constituted gases.

Source: Own manipulation of Climate Watch Data

Fig. 10 percentage distribution of the gases contained in GHG emitted in Nigeria

THE ROLE OF GOVERNMENT IN CCUS TECHNOLOGY ADVANCEMENT (SOUTH AFRICA AND NORWAY)

In order to assess the potential for CCS in South Africa, the South African Centre for Carbon Capture and Storage (SACCCS) was established by the South African Government in 2009 as a public-private sector research collaboration. In conjunction with the establishment of SACCCS, a roadmap for the development of CCS in South Africa was also developed which has five milestones. This Roadmap has since been endorsed by the South African Government Cabinet, SACCCS’s role in the South African CCS Roadmap is as contained in the flowchart below:

The capture and storage of carbon dioxide have been identified as one of the fundamental approaches to mitigating climate change. The Council for Geoscience in South Africa has been at the forefront of CCS innovation since 2010, and has since produced an atlas on the geological storage of the CO₂ in South Africa. The Atlas is the result of cooperation and partnership between Government, State-Owned Entities and the private sector. These include the South African National Energy Research Institute (SANERI), PetroSA, Petroleum Agency of South Africa (all three companies are members of the CEF – Central Energy Fund Group), plus Anglo American, Eskom, Sasol and the Council for Geoscience.

The first steps that the South Africa took in carbon storage was the investigation of potential and the compilation of a detailed Atlas to identify and characterize potential storage site and the building capacity which include both human and technical. So the Centre for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCCS) was established within the South African National Energy Research Institute in order to enable a place that will facilitate the implementation of carbon capture and storage project. The Centre focus are:

- A. Capacity building – technical know – how, injection demonstration and human capacity
- B. Public outreach
- C. Plant ready
- D. Regulatory system
- E. Informed decisions
- F. Sources and geological storage sites
- G. General enabling research and development
- H. Informed decisions

Fig.11 Configuration for Centre for Carbon Capture and Storage Research (M. Cloete et al. 2009)

Furthermore, the type of geological storage site that are being considered by South Africa are the depleted oil and gas wells since the South Africa has a shortage reserves for oil and gas, the little it has is primarily gas which is then later converted into liquid fuels, the un-mineable coal seams is another type of storage site considered by the South Africa and lastly the deep saline aquifers which is considered the best carbon dioxide storage site in South Africa. The

findings of the Atlas are that South Africa has about fifteen (15) Giga tones of storage capacity at theoretical level of which most of the storage is offshore. About 98 % of the storage potential is located in the Mesozoic basins along the coast of the country. The storage potential have been found to lie within the saline formations of the Outeniqua, Orange and Durban basins.

Table 1. Geological Potential for Carbon Dioxide Storage in Deep Saline Aquifers

Area	Name	Gigatonnes CO2
A	Vryheid Formation	183 (0)
B	Free state, KwaZulu Natal & Lesotho	80
C	Molteno & Clarens Formations	24
D & E	E Cape	?
Other	Above – Ground	?
TOTAL		-287 (104) Gt

Fig.12 the result of the Atlas on Geological Storage of CO2 in South Africa

There is a possible deep saline formation storage opportunities within the onshore and offshore in Mesozoic basins along the South Africa, also within the deep coal fields of the Koroo Basin. The storage capacity of the basin and the coals fields are indicated by round symbols (black) and data confidence by purple.

The current phase underway carbon capture and storage project of the South Africa is the Pilot Storage Project which is fully funded by the World Bank and the South Africa Government according to David Khoza, CGS, and South Africa. The main purpose of the project is

to carry out a small-scale CO₂ injection, storage, and monitoring project that includes injection of 10,000 to 50,000 metric tons (MT) over a 2-year period, with monitoring activities to extend beyond injection, increase the human and technical capacity for the development and operation of CO₂ handling, injection and monitoring, to raise awareness of the potential importance of the CCS to the South Africa public. Finally to provide a platform for government to develop a South African CCS legal and regulatory environment.

The South African Government has broken this pilot project into stages of Pre-feasibility, namely; Feasibility (Basin exploration), Feasibility (Site characterization), Design, Procurement and construction, Operation, Closure, and Post-closure.

Fig. 13 The Pilot Carbon dioxide Storage Project stage-gates (Brendan 2014)

In addition, significant achievements have recently been made as regard to the engagement of PCSP stakeholders such as the National Government, Provincial Government, Local Government, Environmental NGOs, the Organized Labour, National House Traditional Leaders, Parliament and Amakhozi [Local Chiefs]. The South African government has aim to launch the pilot carbon capture online in 2023, the project will be based around South Africa's north east, the town of Leandra, Mpumalanga Province, a carbon emissions hotspot.

Similarly, the Norwegian Government has championed the advancement of carbon storage systems development in the country, particularly within the Norwegian section of the North Sea. Norway's investment in CO₂ capture, transport and storage includes a host of activities, from research and development to full demonstration and international advancement of CCS. Norway's Petroleum Directorate explained that CO₂ could be stored on the Norwegian continental shelf. The country does not have any appropriate terrestrial sites but the storage potential beneath its North Sea territorial waters is vast.

Norway has begun work on Project Longship, a €1.7 billion project with the potential to bury vast amounts of captured and store carbon under the North Sea in an effort to slow climate change. The Longship project is the largest climate technology investment in Norwegian Petroleum Industry, it is a full-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS) project that will demonstrate the capture of CO₂ from industrial sources as well as transport and safe storage of CO₂. For example, the illustration of the storage of CO₂ in Norway is as seen in the image contained in fig. 13 below.

Fig. 13. Illustration on how Project Longship would store carbon under the North Sea.

The project is part of Norway's commitment to meet the goals of the 2015 Paris Agreement, which compels signatories to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 in order to give the world a chance of capping global warming at 1.5 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels. It's involves injecting carbon dioxide captured from factory emissions in depleted oil and gas fields (Sleipner and Snohvit). The total cost estimate for Longship (investments and operating cost) is a total of approximately NOK 28bn (\$2.5million). The government's share of the investments and operating costs is estimated around NOK 18bn (\$1.6million) NOK. The Longship project was launched on 21st September 2020, and is described in the white paper Meld. St. 33 (2019 - 2020) 'Longship -Carbon capture and storage'.

Fig.14 Illustration of CO₂ injection and storage on the Sleipner field in the North Sea (Photo: Alligator film/BUG, Equinor)

The gas from the field has a high content of CO₂. During processing of the gas on the platform, CO₂ is separated out and injected into the Utsira formation far below the seabed. Since 1996, up to 11 million tons of CO₂ a year has been stored here. The transport and storage part of the project has been named Northern Light which is owned by France's TotalEnergies, Norway's Equinor and Anglo-Dutch giant Shell. The Northern Lights is responsible for developing and operating CO₂ transport and storage facilities, open to third parties, as part of Longship, the Norwegian Government's full-scale carbon capture and storage project. The plan is to develop Northern Lights in two phases. The first phase is part of the Longship project and has an estimated capacity of 1.5 million tons of CO₂ per year and facilities schedule to come on stream in 2024. A possible second phase would have an estimated capacity of 5 million tons of CO₂ per year.

The Norwegian Government has demonstrated strong, long-standing leadership in realizing full scale CCS. With support of the Norwegian Government, the Northern Lights can provide realistic de-carbonization opportunities for Norwegian and European industries. In 2016 the government then issued feasibility studies on capture, transport and storage solution. Combined, these studies showed the feasibility of putting together the pieces of the value chain and realizing a full-scale CCS project.

Fig. 15 The Longship CCS value chain

WHAT NIGERIA CAN LEARN FROM NORWAY AND SOUTH AFRICA

Nigeria has a lot she can gain or learn from the success recorded by both South Africa and Norway when it comes to the development of carbon capture and storage technologies in the country, this encompasses legislation, funding, incentives for SMEs focusing on carbon capture and storage, monitoring, creation of specified agencies, and an upgrade of the Nigerian Geological Survey Agency into a more robust data driven organization for monitoring and Environmental Impact Assessment. With an investment of \$20b (**19.1 trillion naira**), Nigeria could adequately empower the NGSA into becoming more research based and object oriented institute as regards to CCUS and particularly in the area of storage system development. This could be done in phases as explained in the flowchart below, each of these phases can be said to be the momentary goal of the project, the empowerment of the NGSA will save Nigeria Valuable time and money whilst placing the country on the path of achieving the global vision 2050 of net zero emissions and also fulfilling Nigeria's patch on the Paris agreement of 2015 of which nigeria is one of the signatories to that agreement.

With \$10.5b (8 trillion naira) directly invested in infrastructural development and facility upgrade of some NGSA offices across Nigeria, perhaps on a regional scale, another investment of \$5.5b in equipment for research, such as GIS database, subsurface investigation software (Petrel) and the likes, the remaining \$4b can be channeled into personnel training and capacity building, which will include remuneration review, oversea training, workshops, conference attendance and improved field and laboratory equipment.

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